

Synthesis of New 1-Aryl-2*H*-benzimidazolo[2,1-*e*]imidazoles

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The condensation of *o*-phenylenediamine with glycine in acid medium gave 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole dihydrochloride. The reaction of 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole dihydrochloride with the aromatic aldehydes in alkaline medium afforded fused benzimidazolo[2,1-*e*]imidazole derivatives. They were screened for antimicrobial activity.

A few routes¹ have been introduced for the synthesis of isomeric benzimidazoloimidazole systems 1 and 2 in different methods. Though a number of reports appeared in literature describing the synthesis of benzimidazoloimidazoles but a few are available on their physiological activity. In this connection we report the synthesis of 1-aryl-2*H*-benzimidazolo[2,1-*e*]imidazole derivatives and describe their antimicrobial activity.

The intermediate for the title compounds 2-(aminomethyl)benzimidazole (3) was prepared by the condensation of *o*-phenylenediamine with glycine in acid medium. Compound 3 was treated with aromatic aldehydes in alkaline medium to give 1-aryl-2*H*-benzimidazolo[2,1-*e*]imidazole derivatives. The structures of these compounds were determined by their elemental and spectral data. An attempt to cyclise 2-(α -aminoethyl)benzimidazole was unsuccessful, probably because of steric effect of methyl group.

Results and Discussion

The ir spectra of intermediate showed a sharp peak around 3 550–3 400 cm^{-1} for amino group. The absence of this peak in 4a confirmed the cyclisation. A broad singlet at δ 7.0 which appeared in the pmr spectra of 3 was absent in 4a, which further confirmed cyclisation. The pmr spectra of 1-phenyl-2*H*-benzimidazolo[2,1-*e*]imidazole displayed a neat singlet at δ 2.05 (CH_2), a broad singlet at δ 3.02–3.2 (tertiary proton) and multiplet at δ 7.2–8.1

(ArH). The mass spectra of the title compounds confirmed their structures. The molecular ion peak for 1-phenyl-2*H*-benzimidazolo[2,1-*e*]imidazole (4a) appeared at m/z 235 (30%) and the base peak at m/z 194, which resulted from the molecular ion by the loss of $\text{CH}_2\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ (m/z 41). A further loss of phenyl nucleus gave benzimidazolium ion which appeared at m/z 116. The molecular ion also suffered a direct loss of phenylcyanide (m/z 103) to produce a peak at m/z 132. The latter underwent a further loss of CN radical and was recorded at m/z 106. The peaks of minor importance were omitted.

Biological screening :

Antibacterial activity : All the compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity by Vincent and Vincent filter paper disc technique². The gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria employed were *Bacillus pumilus*, *B. megaterium* and *Proteus vulgaris*, *Sarcina lutea*. All the compounds were found ineffective against all the bacteria, but 4c registered a moderate action against *P. vulgaris*.

The antifungal activity of the compounds was determined by adopting food poisoning technique³. The fungi employed were *Coletotrichum gleosporoides* and *Botryodiplodia theobromene*. Only 4c showed a moderate inhibition at 580 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ against both the fungi, while other compounds were virtually inactive.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on Silica gel-G with benzene–ethyl acetate (2 : 3) solvent system. The ir spectra (nujol) were taken on a Perkin–Elmer 283 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra at C-90 MHz on a EM-390 spectrometer using TMS as internal reference, and mass spectra on a VG-Micro Mass 7070H instrument at 70 eV. Physical and analytical data are given in Table 1.

2-(Aminomethyl)benzimidazole (3) : A mixture of *o*-phenylenediamine (0.01 mol), glycine (0.015 mol) and 5.5 N HCl (100 ml) was refluxed for 30 h

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4

Compd. no.	R	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					O	H	N
4a	Phenyl	72	150-51	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂	76.62 (76.69)	5.51 (5.53)	17.88 (17.87)
4b	p-Chlorophenyl	66	175-76	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ Cl	66.80 (66.79)	4.47 (4.45)	15.57 (15.58)
4c	p-Bromophenyl	62	160-61	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ Br	57.63 (57.62)	3.81 (3.82)	13.40 (13.37)
4d	o-Nitrophenyl	58	135-37	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	64.29 (64.28)	4.27 (4.28)	20.1 (20.0)
4e	p-Nitrophenyl	43	180-81	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	64.30 (64.28)	4.29 (4.28)	20.2 (20.2)
4f	m-Nitrophenyl	45	95-7	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	64.30 (64.28)	4.29 (4.28)	20.2 (20.0)
4g	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	42	140-41	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ Cl ₂	59.42 (59.40)	3.62 (3.63)	13.87 (13.86)
4h	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	55	165-67	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ Cl ₂	59.42 (59.40)	3.64 (3.63)	13.87 (13.86)
4i	p-Hydroxyphenyl	41	175-76	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O	71.72 (71.70)	5.16 (5.17)	16.74 (16.73)
4j	Naphthyl	35	102-04	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂	80.10 (80.00)	5.25 (5.26)	14.74 (14.73)
4k	Furyl	52	110-11	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O	69.34 (69.33)	4.89 (4.88)	18.65 (18.66)

and then cooled and kept overnight. The resulting solid was filtered, dried and purified by the recrystallisation from ethanol to yield 3 (1.21 g, 56%), m.p. 268-70° d; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 550-3 400 sh (NH₂), 1 610-1 590 (C=N), 1 250-1 200 (C-N-C) and 800-650 cm⁻¹ (Ar); δ (DMSO-d₆) 4.9 (s, CH₂), 7.0 (s br, NH₂) and 7.4-8.1 (m, Ar); (m/z) 147 (M⁺, 94%), 119 (100%) and 91 (30%).

1-Aryl-2H-benzimidazolo[2,1-e]imidazoles (4a-k): A mixture of 2-(aminomethyl)benzimidazolo (3; 0.01 mol) and an appropriate aryl aldehyde (0.01 mol) was warmed in 1 N NaOH (30 ml) on a water-bath at 80-90° with occasional shaking for 0.5 h and then the mixture was cooled. The resulting solid was filtered, washed, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

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